

Our Heritage, Our Stories
Workshop Report

W8: Ethics & Data Sharing Models

Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and Searching Community-Generated Digital Content to Develop the People's National Collection

Tate Case Study Report, July 2024

CGDC is currently 'critically endangered' due to technological and organisational barriers and has proven resistant to traditional methods of linking and integration. The challenge of integrating CGDC into larger archives has effectively silenced diverse community voices within our national collection. Our Heritage, Our Stories (OHOS), responds to these urgent challenges by bringing together cutting edge approaches from cultural heritage, humanities, and computer science.

Our Heritage, Our Stories (OHOS) project abstract

This report summarises findings from *The Archive is a Gathering Place*, a case study for Our Heritage, Our Stories (OHOS) that took the form of a public programme at Tate. Building on Tate's commitment to opening collections for cross-collection and cross-disciplinary research, the initiative brought together sixty-four artists, archivists, librarians, researchers and digital practitioners to discuss the future of community-generated digital content (CGDC) and collectively owned archives, particularly those created and sustained by artists and artist collectives. The programme was grounded in histories of collective archiving in Britain.

In her essay 'Living Archives at Tate: After *An Archival Impulse*' as part of Tate's Reshaping the Collectible project, Sarah Haylett defined a community archive as follows:

Community archives are collections of material that document a group of people brought together by a collective commonality – be that an identity, location or interest – and produced and maintained by the self-identifying community ... From an archival literature perspective, it is acknowledged that these are communities that have been excluded from formal archival institutions, and therefore need to document their own experiences and histories.¹

Gathering and organising together to document collective experiences despite being left out of formal and national collections, is a defining factor of CGDC. The Tate programme sought to understand the role of institutions in supporting and the continuation of these

¹ Sarah Haylett, 'Living Archives at Tate: After *An Archival Impulse*', *Reshaping the Collectible: Archives*, Tate Research Publication, 2023, <https://www.tate.org.uk/research/reshaping-the-collectible/archives-living-archives-at-tate-after-an-archival-impulse>, accessed 31 July 2024.

practices as essential to supporting CGDC as part of the National Collection. The barriers identified by the OHOS project and by previous research at Tate – notably histories of institutional racism, paternalism, and the broader colonial context in Britain of oppression, dispossession and erasure – cannot be ignored as we pursue a representative National Collection. They cannot be addressed by technological innovation alone. Collectives and communities that generate CGDC and create collective archives, need to continue to have control over their narratives and representation. The programme adopted a people-centered approach, gathering participants through focus groups, a symposium and a festival to reflect the importance of sustained collective engagement for the preservation of community-owned archives.

Background: Tate, Collective Archives and Community-Generated Digital Content

Tate Library and Archive collections comprise a library of half a million publications on British art since 1500 and international art since 1900, including a range of special collections, Tate Archive and Public Records. Established as a public collection in 1970, Tate Archive has built up a considerable collection of material on artists, art world figures and organisations in Britain. With more than 1,000 separate archive collections it is now the world's largest repository for British art archives. More than 80,000 items from Tate Archive can be viewed online.

Tate's Library and Archive hold several collectively generated special collections/archives, and/or archives representative of collectives or communities. These include the Panchayat Collection and the Making Histories Visible Archive, among others. Over the past five years, the museum has sought to expand access to these collections for audiences, communities of learning and communities of practice. Digital initiatives such as the [Panchayat Collection Research Resource](#) and an ongoing [digitisation project](#) held in collaboration with the keepers of this collection are exemplary of Tate's approach to the post-custodial model.

Learning from previous research projects

Tate's participation in OHOS allowed us to build on learnings from previous research projects into collective and community archiving practice, including [Reshaping the Collectible, Archives and Access](#) and [Provisional Semantics](#).

Archives and Access (2012–17) was a National Lottery Heritage Fund (NLHF) project that enabled a digitisation project, public engagement programme, and a new suite of galleries to display archival holdings together with digitised volumes. To support the discovery of digitised collections, the team created a set of digital resources including the [Animating the Archives film](#)

[series](#), which addressed themes inherent in the collections, and [AnnoTate](#), a tool that invited audiences to transcribe text from the collections. The Albums feature allowed users to collate and share pieces published on Tate's website. The project also resulted in an [Archives and Access Toolkit](#).

Provisional Semantics (February 2020 – 2022) was a Foundational Project within AHRC's [Towards a National Collection \(TANC\)](#) programme. It addressed the challenges of 'representing multiple perspectives within an evolving digitised national collection'. A key finding of the project related to the limitations of relying on digitisation alone for increasing access to collections:

The speed and scale of technologically driven approaches are presented as solutions to increasing and improving access to public collections ... However, our research ... has led us to advocate here for a far more people-centered method to disrupt long-standing but problematic historical narratives and racial hierarchies within museums. Such a method requires a significant investment of time to listen, build relationships, and collaborate to produce rich, multi-perspectival object descriptions, and, in our view, a more careful, or slower approach may aid in this effort.²

Through these projects, researchers at Tate have identified the need to develop new, collaborative and critical approaches to holding these collections. To support the archives, digital products and datasets that its communities are producing, Independent Research Organisations such as Tate require the resources and expertise to build knowledge with the collectives, artists, and audiences they serve.

Tate case study activity

Tate's role as a Project Partner for OHOS addressed a number of the project's aims and objectives, in particular:

- *Undertake an extensive process of **vibrant and inclusive public engagement with stakeholders representing a broad and truly national cross-section of all aspects of community heritage.***

² Kim Balukiewicz, Jane Bramwell, Katie Blackford, Anjalie Dalal-Clayton, Tate Greenhalgh, Helen Mavin, Emily Pringle and Ananda Rutherford, *Provisional Semantics: Addressing the Challenges of Representing Multiple Perspectives within an Evolving Digitised National Collection* (Version 2), 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7081347>, accessed 31 July 2024.

- ***Co-design and prototype post-custodial models of archive management with partner and collaborating organisations and the extensive community of practice working with this material.***

The case study focused on the following areas:

- Exploring how public programming and gathering people across various disciplines and research areas, including the arts to discuss CGDC can help strengthen ideas, relationships, understanding and collaborative approaches to the post custodial model.
- Exploring how we can learn from participatory approaches to help overcome organisational barriers to integrating and providing equitable access to CGDC.
- Considering what the future of archives that are collectively owned or created could look like and what the role of IROs and formal archives could be in this future.
- Holding space to discuss how archiving organisations, especially those in the public sector can foster collaboration in the generation and preservation of community archiving practice and CGDC.
- Understanding the needs of collectives and artists who are generating CGDC or working to digitise their collections.
- Exploring how we can best serve communities who generate and sustain our national collections, especially those who have been historically excluded from the National Collection.

Research Questions

Through engagement with a variety of community-owned archives, artists, researchers, and initiatives, the study aimed to explore both the digital and the physical archive as a place for people to gather. As such, the **research questions** we set out to investigate were:

Archives held and created by communities have historically been gathering spaces; and while these histories of gathering are held in the collections, how can institutions such as Tate continue to honour the role the archives have played in the everyday lives of the communities they belong to? How can they continue to actively provide space for collective learning, imagination, and self-determination?

The Archive is a Gathering Place Programme

1. **Focus groups – closed sessions:**

Three artist-led conversations were held in February 2024 and took the form of forums designed to share experience, learnings and practice. With 32 participants, they built networks to foster collective and speculative thinking about the futures of CGDC³

2. Symposium – public session:

A symposium was held on 24 May 2024 in the Starr Auditorium at Tate Modern, with three panel conversations and 15 speakers. The three panels were:

- **Digital Futures** – with presentations exploring decentralised platforms for CGDC, questions of language, identity and access on the internet, and digitisation as a tool to protect archives at risk.
- **Holding Collections** – with presentations about the duties of care of institutions, archivists and researchers who are responsible for collective archives.
- **Responding to Collections** – with presentations about how web developers, designers, artists and curators can creatively respond to collections and create platforms in the digital realm, to make them more accessible.

3. Performance Festival – public session:

This event on 25 May 2024 involved commissioned artist performances, archive displays, conversations, workshops and screenings. There were a total of 17 contributors.

Contributors

The Archive is a Gathering Place engaged 64 contributors and included artists whose work is part of the archive at Tate, filmmakers, community organisers and academics, as well as artists, researchers and archivists/librarians at all stages of their careers.

These individuals reflected a variety of practices in relation to the research questions. They represented a wide range of disciplines, subject positions, lived experience and expertise. They were either already working with CGDC or engaging in collective archiving practice. All contributors had previously engaged with ideas around the impact of digitisation on collections and associated approaches, methods, risks and possibilities. Their practices sought to raise questions and offer critical solutions to issues of access, decoloniality and digital archiving/preservation as a mode to resist erasure.

Communities of practice represented included artist collectives, archivists and administrators, preservation and digitisation researchers, community networks and people working at the

³ See Focus Group report

intersection of technology, web development and the galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM) sector. For the full programme description and list of contributors, please see the Appendix. Selected contributors include:

Anasuya Sengupta – co-Director and co-founder of Whose Knowledge?, a global multilingual campaign to centre the knowledges of marginalised communities (the minoritised majority of the world) online.

Ajamu X and Topher Campbell – co-founders of rukus! Federation and the rukus! Black Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer + Archive.

Ellie Porter – an independent practitioner working with artists' archives and organisations, previously Head of Programme at Art360 Foundation, which supported over 50 artists and estates in the creation of archives and legacy strategies.

Janice Cheddie FRSA – a London-based writer, researcher and consultant. Between the mid-1990s and 2015 she was custodian of the

Panchayat Collection, with the artist and curator Shaheen Merali, until its transfer to the Tate Library in 2015. Since 2015 Janice has been a member of ICOMOS-UK's Intangible Cultural Heritage committee.

Kaitlene Koranteng – archivist, engagement producer and poet, project Archivist for Transforming the National Collection Project UAL Decolonising the Arts Institute (2022–3).

Mindy Seu – designer, technologist and educator, creator of the Cyberfeminism Index, which gathers three decades of online activism and net art.

SITAAD Collective – artistic collaboration initiated by archivists Leyla Degan and Naima Hassan in 2022

Audience

Friday: 199 tickets + 50 guests

Saturday: 244 tickets + c.150 museum visitors*

*The event was free and open to Tate visitors. Estimate provided by the Tate Modern Visitor Experience team.

The symposium and performance festival were public events open to all. The symposium was attended by both a general and a research-engaged audience. The audience included:

- Students, artworkers and curators, archivists, established artists, and UK university educators and researchers.
- Researchers and artists interested in or part of artist collectives who had used archiving as a mode of resistance against marginalisation by national institutions.
- Researchers and practitioners creating CGDC.
- Researchers engaging with questions of preservation and digital futures of collective archives and CGDC.
- Practitioners including youth workers, oral historians and community organisers.

The festival welcomed young people (those under the age of 25), families with children, and older members of the public. Some of them approached the organisers of the event to express that they had not visited Tate before. The audience was active and participated in discussions after the talks, approaching organisers and Tate staff to share their thoughts about the programme and ask questions.

Audience feedback

Signage at the event encouraged visitors to send thoughts, questions and feedback to the Tate Research inbox. A selection of comments is included below:

- *'The Archive is a Gathering Place* expanded my thoughts on what archives are, what they do and what they can be ... Most importantly, it was a wake-up call to me: we do not create archives in vain. We create archives because we are alive and full of life, because we are active participants in the communities we interact with, and because – quite simply – because we are here, and that matters.' – Audience Member
- *'[The Archive is a Gathering Place]* was excellent and I greatly enjoyed both the more conventionally conference themed first day and the more practice-oriented Saturday. As someone researching Global Majority arts archives (and former library worker) it brought together multiple strands of thinking and it was wonderful to see so many former colleagues and collaborators as well as be introduced to projects that were previously new to me.' – Audience Member
- *'I particularly appreciated (as someone who researches and works in/with art pedagogies) that artistic and creative practices were at the forefront of the whole event...[my research] considers the communal as much as methodological implications of using archives actively, particularly in relation to art, art history + the current/ongoing educational crisis, so it was wonderful to be brought together with so many others working similarly.'*

Participant and audience feedback on the programme was clear in its message: people working with collective archives and CGDC would like more opportunities to come together to share practice, research, and resources.

Methodology: How can institutions like Tate better facilitate contributions of the community that could be part of a national collection?

- **Amplifying artists' voices**

The programme was shaped by three artist-led focus groups in February, which highlighted the importance of artists' voices in collective movements for self-determination in the UK from the 1980s. The events supported this through commissioning practice-based research from artists alongside more traditional papers.

- **Transdisciplinarity**

A co-curatorial approach, highlighting the connections between communities, artists, designers, technologists and archivists/librarians allowed for a sharing of ideas beyond disciplines, and the

Fig.2 Dr. Christine Eyene, who worked with Lubaina Himid CBE RA on the Making Histories Visible Archive, in conversation with Adrian Glew, Tate Archivist. Photo © Lawrie Phillips

- **Platforming existing networks and institutions**

Archives and organisations whose innovative methods, approaches and platforms for CGDC were featured in the programme included Iniva, June Givanni Panafrican Cinema Archive, Mayday Rooms, Whose Knowledge? Collective, Women’s Art Library, Goldsmiths, the Making Histories Visible Archive (Tate Archive), the Panchayat Collection (Tate Library), the Columbia University Archive and the Rita Keegan Archive.

Fig.3 Audiences watching a screening organised by the June Givanni Panafrican Cinema Archive. Photo © Lawrie Phillips

Conclusions

What does this case study tell us about the contributions of the community that could be part of a national collection, and how can it inform approaches to community-generated digital content?

1. Institutions must platform the context, practices and knowledge surrounding community contributions to national collections

The life worlds, teachings, practices and environments that surround CGDC are essential to its meaning. Creating space for public engagement in our museums, as well as the digital outputs, platforms and communication we generate for this context and practice-sharing is vital for communicating CGDC with our publics.

2. More opportunities are needed for people working with collective archives and community-generated digital content (CGDC) to share practices, research, and resources

Organisations like Tate can play a unique role in opening up the conversation about CGDC to a wider audience. Tate's galleries, library, archive and online platform, is a key mediator between communities and the national collection, both in the digital and physical realm.

3. Grassroots organisations are essential partners

Grassroots libraries, archives and collectives are sector-leading in innovation around CGDC and sustain strong networks with their communities of practice. Larger museums, galleries, and IROs can most effectively contribute to the preservation and linking of CGDC in the first instance, by engaging in their work, building networks across institutions to share resources, platforms and forums.

4. Research engagement with communities of practice requires a long-term and equitable approach

To repeat a recommendation made in the evaluation of the Provisional Semantics project, histories of erasure, neglect and colonialism have eroded trust between some communities and institutions. Working collaboratively means investing time to 'work slowly' with stakeholders. Programming or acquisition of community-generated content should be supported by research that is collaborative, practice-based and long-term.

5. Representation of communities in decision-making processes is crucial for developing ethical collaboration frameworks

Bringing stakeholders into research and planning processes from the outset of a project builds trust, collaboration and builds better outputs. Communities of practice are best placed to shape programme that speaks to their audiences.

6. **Histories and methods of collective archiving need to be considered in with modern digital preservation techniques**

Participants advocated approaching CGDC as a continuation or and evolution of methods of gathering, resistance, collective action and support, pioneered by community archiving practices.

References

Sarah Haylett, 'Living Archives at Tate: After *An Archival Impulse* ', *Reshaping the Collectible: Archives*, Tate Research Publication, 2023, <https://www.tate.org.uk/research/reshaping-the-collectible/archives-living-archives-at-tate-after-an-archival-impulse>, accessed 31 July 2024.

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Towards a National Collection, <https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk>, accessed 2 August 2024.

- **Tate Focus Group report reference to be included here –**

Tate Team

Steering Committee: Kim Balukiewicz, Martha Barratt, Jane Bramwell, David Dibosa, Adrian Glew, Gustavo Grandal Montero

Project Lead: Vasundhara Mathur

Appendix

1. Project Description

Collective archives are created out of a necessity to document, preserve and mobilise perspectives, dreams, testimonies, narratives and practices that might otherwise be lost, or face active erasure. They are enabled by the gathering together and organising of both people and material. The collective archive is not simply a collection of objects and ephemera, but a result of ‘human infrastructures,’ networks and relationships. Archival practices emerge in this context as continuous practices of communing, ‘dream-keeping’, collaboration and resistance.

Engaging with the rich history and present iterations of grassroots and digital archiving projects, ‘The Archive is a Gathering Place’ invites audiences to a collective, interdisciplinary conversation that engages with the archive as a public, gathering place and archiving as a creative and political practice. In the context of an international art gallery and museum, the project also explores how artists work with, activate and unleash archives to image, imagine and give language to radical futures, through an engagement with the past.

Additionally, the project asks: How can histories of gathering around archives, or gathering *to* archive, inform the duties of care and protection towards these collections across disciplines and practices? The project is critically concerned with questions of access, preservation/protection, and what it means to care for collectively owned digital archives that face precarity.

Programme of activity

By gathering with and listening to people who care for community archives in different ways – including artists, archivists, writers and community organisers – this project explores how the preservation of community-owned archives requires sustained collective engagement.

Activities include:

- Three artist-led seminars in February 2024
- A [symposium and a public performance and collective archive festival](#) at Tate Modern on 24 and 25 May 2024

Partners

‘The Archive is a Gathering Place’ forms part of [Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and searching community-generated digital content to develop the people’s national collection](#), a Discovery Research Project funded by **the Arts and Humanities Research Council**, as part of the [Towards a National Collection](#) programme. **Our Heritage Our Stories** is led by Lorna Hughes at the

University of Glasgow in collaboration with the University of Manchester, The National Archives and the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC).

Tate's contribution to *Our Heritage Our Stories* as a project partner is led by Vasundhara Mathur (Assistant Research Editor, Tate Research) with support from Tate Library and Archive.

2. Symposium Programme 24 May 2024

The symposium took place 10.30–17.00 at Tate Modern in the Starr Auditorium.

10.30 Opening remarks: Vasundhara Mathur: David Dibosa: Director Tate Research, Curator and Project Lead, Abigail Glen: OHOS Representative

11.00 Panel 1: *Access and Futurity*

Rosemary Grennan: Building the Archive as a Common Resource

Rosemary Grennan is a member of the MayDay Rooms collective – an archive dedicated to the history of social struggles, resistance campaigns and experimental culture. The main work of MayDay Rooms consists in connecting historical materials with contemporary political struggles through collaborative education and research, digitisation, and free distribution. She is interested in developing platforms and practices which aid different forms of collective engagement with historical material. She has recently been working on a collaborative online repository of political ephemera called leftover.rs. She is also the co-founder of AGIT, a residency space in Berlin focusing on social movement history and culture.

Anasuya Sengupta: Whose Heritage? Whose Knowledge?: our journey of liberatory memory work

Anasuya Sengupta is co-Director and co-founder of Whose Knowledge?, a global multilingual campaign to centre the knowledges of marginalised communities (the minoritised majority of the world) online. She is a co-founder and advisor to Numun Fund (the first feminist tech fund for and from the Global South), the former Chief Grantmaking Officer at the Wikimedia Foundation, and the former Regional Program Director at the Global Fund for Women. Anasuya is a 2017 Shuttleworth Foundation Fellow and received a 2018 Internet and Society award from the Oxford Internet Institute. She is on the Scholars' Council for UCLA's Center for Critical Internet Inquiry and the advisory committee for MIT's Center for Research on Equitable and Open Scholarship (CREOS)

Alia Al-Sabi: Captive Archives in Palestine

Alia Al-Sabi will provide a brief glimpse of an archive of books and notebooks recording the textual practices and literary production of the Palestinian Prisoners' Movement in the 1970s and 1980s. Al-Sabi is a writer and researcher based in Brooklyn, New York. She is currently a PhD Candidate in the Performance Studies department at NYU, where she is researching prison literatures in various archives in Palestine. Her research focus considers theories of movement and subversion within logics of surveillance and confinement through examining the textual practices produced within carceral structures.

Janice Cheddie: Chair

Janice Cheddie FRSA is a London-based writer, researcher and consultant. Janice was born in St Lucia, West Indies, and migrated to London as a child with her mother and older brother. She is a part of the 'Children of Windrush' generation, a collective generational experience that has been influential in shaping contemporary Britain. Between the mid-1990s and 2015 she was custodian of the Panchayat Collection, with the artist and curator Shaheen Merali, until its transfer to the Tate Library in 2015. Since 2015 Janice has been a member of ICOMOS-UK's Intangible Cultural Heritage committee. Between 2020 and 2022 Janice was research consultant for London-based AFFORD, Return of the Icons initiative, funded by the Open Society Foundation. Return of the Icons seeks the restitution of looted African artefacts and human remains within UK museums and heritage institutions to their communities of origin.

13.30 Panel 2: *Holding Collections: Archiving as Dreamkeeping*

Tao Leigh Goffe and Eddie Bruce-Jones: Mangrove as Caribbean Method in Two Acts

Tao Leigh Goffe (Cornell) and Eddie Bruce-Jones (SOAS) offer remarks situated at the intersection of environmental/ecological issues and epistemological questions in engaging with the archive. After introducing the conceptual terrain of their own research, Goffe and Bruce-Jones move into a discussion of their joint work; an interdisciplinary digital humanities project that uses the indentureship period as a window for exploring new methodological questions and approaches for historical analysis of colonialism and the contemporary theorisation of diaspora and global problems.

Thai Jones: *Beyond Wonder: Teaching with Anger and Outrage in the Archives*

Thai Jones is the Curator for History at Columbia University's archive. He teaches critical research and the history of radicalism, and is the author of several books, including *More Powerful Than Dynamite: Radicals, Plutocrats, Progressives, and New York's Year of Anarchy* (2014) and *A Radical Line: From the Labor Movement to the Weather Underground, One Family's Century of Conscience* (2004). He served as historical consultant and co-writer on the award-winning podcast *Mother Country Radicals* (2022). His writing has appeared in a variety of national US publications, including *The New Yorker*, the *Washington Post*, the *New York Times*, *The Nation* and the *Occupied Wall Street Journal*.

Christine Eyene: The George Hallett Research Collection

Christine Eyene will discuss the formation of an independent research collection bringing together works by South African photographer George Hallett (1942–2020) focusing on South African exile and Black communities in Britain and beyond in the 1970s and 1980s. She will address issues around the preservation of archives marginalised by mainstream institutions and

how these reflect the state of art histories and practices neglected by dominant narratives. Eyene will also share how her 10-year collaboration with artist and Professor of Contemporary Art Lubaina Himid CBE RA, in the framework of Making Histories Visible, enabled her to care for, research, and disseminate Hallett's work and contribution to South African, British, and Diasporic art histories.

Ellie Porter: Chair

Ellie Porter was previously Head of Programme at Art360 Foundation, which supported over 50 artists and estates in the creation of archives and legacy strategies. From 2017 - 2023 she ran a public programme of curatorial residences in artists' archives, collaborative research initiatives and professional development opportunities for archivists. Ellie co-produced documentary films on artists' legacies with filmmakers, as well as toolkits and a mobile app for archiving with project partners including; the International Curators Forum, The National Archives, the Showroom, Hauser & Wirth Institute, Flat Time House and the Women's Art Library.

14.45 Panel 3: *Responding to the Archive*

Aleema Gray: Liberating the Archive

Aleema Gray is a Jamaican-born curator, researcher and public historian based in London. She was awarded the Yesu Persaud Scholarship for her PhD entitled *Bun Babylon: A Community-engaged History of Rastafari in Britain*. Aleema's work focuses on documenting Black history in Britain through the perspective of lived experiences. Her practice is driven by a concern for more historically contingent ways of understanding the present, especially in relation to notions of belonging, memory, and contested heritage. She is the Lead Curator for *Beyond the Bassline: 500 years of Black British Music* at the British Library and the founder of *House of Dread*, an anti-disciplinary heritage studio.

Abeera Kamran: Urdu Newspapers: The Archive is Still in Print

The continued importance of traditional and historical ways of arranging text belies Urdu's fraught relationship with typesetting technologies. Urdu newspapers handwritten and lithographed as late as 1981 to maintain the calligraphic aesthetics readers had come to expect. In this talk Abeera Kamran will discuss how the design of contemporary Urdu newspapers keeps archival modes of reading and seeing alive and vibrant for the Urdu reader, and how inadequate digital technologies threaten this sophisticated design tradition.

Abeera Kamran is a designer, web developer and researcher. She works between Birmingham, UK and Karachi, Pakistan. She is an AHRC funded PhD student at the Department of Typography and Graphic Communication, at the University of Reading. Her research investigates the design

and technological challenges associated with publishing Urdu in responsive web environments. She is also a lecturer in Design at the University of Reading.

Mindy Seu: The Cyberfeminism Index

Mindy Seu is a designer and technologist based in New York City and Los Angeles. Her expanded practice involves archival projects, techno-critical writing, performative lectures, design commissions, and close collaborations. Her latest writing surveys feminist economies, historical precursors of the metaverse, and the materiality of the internet. Mindy's ongoing Cyberfeminism Index, which gathers three decades of online activism and net art, was commissioned by Rhizome, presented at the New Museum, and awarded the Graham Foundation Grant. She has lectured internationally at cultural institutions (Barbican Centre, New Museum), academic institutions (Columbia University, Central Saint Martins).

16:00 rukus!: A conversation between Topher Campbell and Ajamu X

Ajamu X is an artist, scholar, archive curator and radical sex activist. His [fine art photography](#) explores same-sex desire and the Black male body. He is the co-founder of rukus! Federation and the rukus! Black Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer + Archive.

Topher Campbell is a filmmaker, artist and writer who has created a range of works in broadcasting, film, theatre, television and performance. His works focus on issues of sexuality, masculinity and the city, particularly in relation to race, human rights and climate change. He is the co-founder of rukus! Federation and the rukus! Black Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer + Archive.

FESTIVAL PROGRAMME – 25 MAY

All day: The June Givanni Panafrican Cinema Archive will present a selection from its holdings which both converge with, and critically intervene into Tate's collections. The archive invites visitors to a gathering space of films, reading material and other memorabilia.

11.00–12.00 Workshop with Lamya Sadiq (MayDay Rooms) and Jordan Taylor (PageMasters): Pamphlet Making in the Digital Age

Join Lamya, Jordan and participants from the MayDay Rooms x PageMasters Print Residency for a collective pamphlet-making session in response to the MayDay Rooms archive. Together, participants will consider questions around the materiality of pamphlets, or zines, as low cost & democratic models of spreading information and forging solidarities, as well as their function and impact in our increasingly digitised world.

12.10–12.55 Archives panel chaired by Althea Greenan (Women's Art Library, Goldsmiths)

Althea Greenan works in Special Collections and Archives at Goldsmiths, University of London curating the Women's Art Library (WAL) collection. She programmes artistic research through supporting artists, students and academics working with the wide range of materials and archives in the WAL. This work is the subject of a film by Holly Antrum commissioned by the Art360 Foundation titled Yes to the Work!: The Women's Art Library <https://www.art360foundation.org.uk/media>.

Additional roles include co-curating the Animating Archives website <https://sites.gold.ac.uk/animatingarchives/> and sitting on the Advisory Board of *Feminist Art Making Histories*, an oral history, digital humanities project, funded by the Irish Research Council and the AHRC.

13.05–14.05 Readings and Music

Zena Agha and Kareem Samara
dove (Chris Kirubi) and Rhoda Boateng
Kaitlene Koranteng

14.05–15.05 Screening and talk by June Givanni Panafrican Cinema Archive

15.05–16.00 SITAAD (Leyla Degan and Naima Hassan): *Letters to Giorgio and Mohamed: Entangled Biographies and Xirsi as a Counter-Archival Method*

The performance presentation *Letters to Giorgio and Mohamed* weaves together historical sound recordings, archival traces, bureaucratic records and critical fabulations relating to the Somali-Italian partisan Giorgio Marincola and to the Somali ethnographic performer and linguist

Mohamed Nur. Opening with cassette tapes recorded by SITAAD in Milan and Berlin, the performance is a sonic dialogue between Leyla Degan and Naima Hassan.

16.10–17.00 Rita Keegan and Lauren Craig: *Preservation as Creation*

The performance is a live digitisation of ephemera from the Rita Keegan Archive, reflecting on the labour, practice and methods of collective archiving and preservation.

Rita Keegan works across print, photography, film, sound, textiles and installation. Her work considers the representation of Black communities historically and acts of self-fashioning in relation to the experience of Black women, often through self-portraiture. In 1984 Rita co-founded Community CopyArt, a resource centre set up to facilitate activist workshops and produce print materials, and in 1985, she established the Women Artists of Colour Index, to catalogue, document and remember the work of Black women artists. Rita's contributions to archival practice were explored by X Marks the Spot in the 2015 publication [*Human Endeavour: a creative finding aid for the Women of Colour Index*](#). In 2020 Rita's archive was presented at [South London Gallery](#), followed by a solo exhibition of her work curated by the [Rita Keegan Archive Project](#). This show was accompanied by [Mirror Reflecting Darkly](#), a new essay collection and archival sourcebook edited by Ego Ahaiwe-Sowinski, Matthew Harle and Rita Keegan. Until April 8th 2024, Rita's work is showing [Women In Revolt! Tate Britain, curated by Linsey Young](#). She is supported in the studio by Lauren Craig, Gina Nembhard, and Naomi Pearce.

Lauren Craig's practice intentionally moves slowly between curation, performance, installation, art writing, moving images and auto-para-ethno-therapeutic photography. Through collaborative live engagement, systems re-thinking and social archival histories, she elevates lived experience as a tool for reframing past and present underexposed narratives. She conceived the conceptual modality S:E:P:A:L:S and is a member of the eponymous constellation which, through live events and publications, explores how we can create 'ethical cultural memory' within curating, institutional decision-making, commissioning and (un)learning. Lauren founded and directed six creative organisations that engaged with ethical, social, environmental, cultural production, and reproductive justice.

Featured

Interventions and displays by [June Givanni – PanAfrican Cinema Archive](#); [Women's Art Library, Goldsmiths](#); [MayDay Rooms](#); [Panchayat Collection](#); [PageMasters](#); [Making Histories Visible Archive](#), among others.

For further information on the programme see: [the events page](#).

